

Antibacterial Activity of Bacteriocin from *Pediococcus pentosaceus* Strain 2397 and Application as Biopreservative for Fishballs

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Meatballs are one of the most popular processed meats in various countries. The meats commonly used to make meatballs are beef, chicken, and fish. The purposes of this study were to evaluate the nitrogen, carbon, and Tween sources on the growth and antimicrobial activity of bacteriocin of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 and to assess the quality of fish balls preserved with bacteriocin from *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 during initial storage at freezing temperature in -18°C . The experimental design used in this study was a factorial, completely randomized design. There were two factors, *i.e.* bacteriocin concentrations (0, 0.15, 0.30, 0.45, and 0.60%) and storage time (0, 3, 6, and 9 d). Data obtained were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and continued with Duncan multiple range test (DMRT) at 5% level. Meanwhile, data on microbiological counts were tabulated and analyzed descriptively. The data showed that the addition of various nitrogen, carbon, or Tween sources did not significantly ($p > 0.05$) affect the growth of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397. The addition of peptone, beef extract or ammonium sulfate, lactose, or Tween 80 into the de Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe broth (MRSB) significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased the bacteriocin antimicrobial activity of strain 2397 against *E. coli*. Using 0.60% bacteriocin produced fish balls according to the quality standard of fish balls and maintained the quality of fish balls during initial storage for 9 d at freezing temperatures.

Keywords: antimicrobial activity, bacteriocin, fish balls, frozen temperature, natural biopreservative, *Pediococcus pentosaceus*

INTRODUCTION

Meatballs are processed meat widely consumed in several nations, including Indonesia. Beef, pork, or chicken are the most frequent meats used to produce meatballs. Fish balls are also prepared from fish meat (Huda *et al.* 2001; Morsy *et al.* 2017). The selection of fish meat must meet specific criteria; for example, the meat must be white to manufacture high-quality fish balls that people enjoy (Fauziyah 2019). Catfish is a fish used as a raw material

for fish balls. Catfish has been successfully cultivated commercially in various nations, making it one of the most popular fishery products. Indonesian catfish production totaled 319,967 tons, with Riau Province accounting for 23,190 tons (Indonesian Central Statistics Agency 2021). Catfish is high in protein and has a tremendous and savory flavor, making it ideal for making fish balls (Huda *et al.* 2010; Rahardianto *et al.* 2012).

In fish balls, nitrite is widely used as a preservative. Long-term exposure to 150 parts per million nitrate is harmful to people's health since it can lead to cancer

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(WHO 2011). Natural preservatives have to be created to reduce the number of chemical preservatives in processed foods. Consumers are becoming more worried about the impact of their food choices on their health. Allergies, behavioral changes, and carcinogenic effects are linked to these impacts, leading to the preference for fresh and natural foods processed with minimal or no synthetic ingredients (Balciunas *et al.* 2013). Biopreservation is essential for preserving meat and meat products' microbiological quality and safety. This method involves inserting a protective microbiota such as lactic acid bacteria (LAB) with antibacterial characteristics such as bacteriocin production into food to extend its shelf life (G'alvez *et al.* 2007).

In this context, a biopreservative is a natural preservative such as bacteriocin. The process of using LAB and its antimicrobial chemicals such as bacteriocin to prevent hazardous and spoilage bacteria from developing in food is known as bio-preservation (Stiles 1996). Bacteriocins are antibacterial chemicals produced by numerous LAB and other bacterial species *via* ribosome synthesis. Bacteriocins are antibiotics that inhibit closely related bacteria and food-borne pathogens (Saeed *et al.* 2014). Bacteriocin is a 12–100 amino acid peptide molecule having amphiphilic characteristics and a cationic net charge produced and released to act extracellularly and kill bacteria (Rios *et al.* 2016). These peptides are GRAS (generally recognized as safe), and their future use in the pharmaceutical and food sectors continues to excite the interest of many scientists. Bacteriocin has long been used to prevent food spoilage and food-borne infections in the food industry (Perez *et al.* 2014). These bacteriocins have various qualities that make them excellent for use as natural food preservatives – including high stability, minimal toxicity, and a narrow to a broad spectrum of activity (Bharti *et al.* 2015). Bacteriocin generated by *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 has a molecular weight of 14.4 kDa and can inhibit *S. aureus* and *Listeria monocytogenes* (Pato *et al.* 2020a, 2021b).

The cell-free supernatant and bacteriocin from many strains of LAB isolated from *dadih*, including *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397, were reported to inhibit the growth of *E. coli* in a prior study (Pato *et al.* 2021a). However, because this strain's antimicrobial activity is limited, it is essential to identify ways to boost it such as using different nutritional sources. *E. coli* is a Gram-negative *Brevibacterium* found in intestinal tracts in people and animals. This bacterium species was initially thought to be largely nonpathogenic, with researchers believing it only produced diarrhea under specific circumstances (Singleton 1999; Tenailon *et al.* 2010). Although most *E. coli* strains are innocuous, some serotypes can cause acute food poisoning in their hosts and are linked to product recalls due to food contamination (CDC 2012; Vogt and Dippold 2005). Because cells can only survive for a short period outside the body, they can evaluate environmental samples for fecal contamination (Feng *et al.* 2002; Thompson 2007). Because of the regular outbreaks of microbial diseases, food-borne pathogens have become critical social problems that have gotten much attention from consumers and food safety regulatory bodies worldwide.

The objectives of this study were to analyze the effect of nitrogen, carbon, and Tween sources on the growth and antimicrobial activity of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 bacteriocin and evaluate the quality of fish balls preserved with *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 bacteriocin during initial storage at freezing temperature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw Materials, Media, and Chemicals

Cultured catfish (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*) weighing in the range of 300–325 g and a length at 25–30 cm was the primary raw material used to produce fish balls. Tapioca, garlic, table salt, pepper, and ice were also used to make fish balls. The composition of the fish balls formula is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of fishball formula.

Raw materials and ingredients	Formula and bacteriocin concentration				
	0%	.0,15%	0.30%	0.45%	0.60%
Catfish fillet (g)	200	200	200	200	200
Garlic (g)	4	4	4	4	4
Pepper (g)	2	2	2	2	2
Ice (g)	40	40	40	40	40
Tapioca (g)	50	50	50	50	50
Table salt (g)	4	4	4	4	4
Bacteriocin (g)	0	0,3	0,6	0,9	1,2

The MRSB and other media for microbiological analysis were used to activate *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 and enumerate the number of microbes among the substances employed. Ammonium sulfate, phosphate buffers, and other compounds for proximate analysis.

***Pediococcus pentosaceus* strain 2397 and *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19**

P. pentosaceus strain 2397 was isolated from *dadih* from Bukittinggi, West Sumatera, Indonesia (Hosono *et al.* 1989). The Gram-positive pathogenic bacterium used was *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 was obtained from Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia.

Activation of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 and *E. coli* FNCC 15

The activation of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 and *E. coli* FNCC-19 cultures were carried out according to the method described in our previous work (Pato *et al.* 2021a). *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 culture was transferred to a test tube containing 5-mL MRSB, shaken evenly, and incubated at 37 °C for 18 h. Inoculating 0.1 mL into a 5-mL nutrient broth, shaking evenly, and incubating for 18 h at 37 °C yielded an active culture of *E. coli* FNCC-19.

Production of Bacteriocin

By inoculating 2.5% of the active culture and incubating for 24 h at 37 °C, *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 was grown in MRSB. The broth was then centrifuged for 15 min at 10,000 rpm to get the supernatant. The supernatant was combined with 70% ammonium sulfate and placed in the refrigerator (4 °C) for 12 h to precipitate the protein. This mixture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 min at 4 °C to get crude bacteriocin (Sankar *et al.* 2012).

***In Vitro* Antimicrobial Activity of *P. pentosaceus* Strain 2397**

P. pentosaceus strain 2397 was grown in MRSB and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h aerobically. The indicator bacteria, *E. coli* FNCC-19, was raised in NB for 24 h at 37 °C. The indicator bacterium was put into a 100-L container and then flattened with a hockey stick until fully dry. A well was then made and covered with sterile agar using a sterile blue tip. Each well was filled with 100 mL of bacteriocins and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The clear zone's diameter was then measured (Pato *et al.* 2017).

Preparation of Fishballs

Fish balls were produced according to Sinaga *et al.* (2017). Catfish fillets were cut into and immersed in cold water for 40 min at 5 °C in a 1:3 (w/v) meat-to-water ratio. In addition, a knife was used to cut the fat from the catfish

fillet. After trimming the catfish fillet, the meat was ground in a grinder until pulverized. The fish meat was added with spices (2% each of pepper, garlic, sugar, and salt) into the dough, then blended again. Additionally, while stirring and crushing 200 g of catfish, 50 g tapioca flour was gradually added until a homogeneous dough was formed. Furthermore, bacteriocin was added to the fish balls dough in proportion to the treatment – namely, 0 (control), 0.15, 0.30, 0.40, and 0.60% (w/w) of the fishball dough. The dough was made of fish balls with a diameter of about 2.5 cm and an average weight of 15 g. The fish balls were cooked for 10–15 min in hot water until they floated. The fishball samples were then packed in polyethylene bags and stored at freezing temperature (approximately –18 °C) for physical, microbiological, and sensory analysis at 0, 3, 6, and 9 d.

Chemical and Microbiological Analysis

Chemical components such as water and ash were examined using AOAC guidelines (1999). Total plate count and the amount of *S. aureus* were determined using the surface dish method according to AOAC (2005), whereas those of *E. coli* were determined using the MPN technique according to ISO 7251 (2005).

Ethical Approval

This experimental study on sensory analysis was conducted under the approval of the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Nursing, Universitas Riau, Pekanbaru, Indonesia (No. 156/UN.19.5.1.8/KEPK.FKp/2021).

Sensory Analysis

Ten (10) students from the Department of Agricultural Technology, Faculty of Agriculture, Universitas Riau, Pekanbaru, Indonesia, conducted a sensory analysis as a descriptive test. The samples were given out at random and were coded. The sensory evaluation consisted of serving samples of fish balls each having a 2.5-cm diameter, divided into four halves, and served on clean plates with random numbers. Each panelist was asked to rate the descriptive test's quality features based on sight, smell, taste, and texture. For the taste test, panelists were given plain water to function as a tongue cleanser, ensuring that the subsequent sample was unaffected by the prior one (Setyaningsih *et al.* 2010).

Experimental Design and Data Analysis

This study was conducted in an experimental setting with a completely randomized design. Treatments for LAB growth and antibacterial action included five sources of sugar, four nitrogen sources, and three Tween sources. Fish balls were subjected to five different

bacteriocin concentration treatments and stored at freezing temperature for 9 d. All of the research treatments were carried out three times. The data on the growth of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397, antimicrobial activity of bacteriocin, chemical composition, and sensory analysis of fish balls were statistically examined using ANOVA and then DMRT at the 5% level using SPSS Software Version 23. In the meantime, data on the microbiological counts of fish balls were collected and descriptively analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

P. pentosaceus strain 2397 was cultivated at various nitrogen sources, and bacteriocin produced was tested against *E. coli* (Figure 1). With or without different

nitrogen sources, the development of strain 2397 showed nearly identical absorbance values (Figure 1A). This fact was owing to the MRSB medium carrying enough N for LAB, including strain 2397, to thrive. Although carbohydrates were not required for bacteriocin synthesis, they were needed for growth (Parlindungan *et al.* 2021). The addition of four types of N sources significantly ($p < 0.05$) improved the antibacterial activity of strain 2397 against *E. coli*, despite the growth showing very identical absorbance values (Figure 1B). The addition of peptone showed the highest activity, followed by beef extract and ammonium sulfate, and yeast extract showed the lowest antimicrobial activity of the bacteriocin produced by *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397. The results showed that using 10 g/L of soy peptone in the growth medium of *L. lactis* SM526 produced 31.12 mg/L of nisin (Juturu and Wu

Figure 1. Growth and antimicrobial activity of bacteriocin of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 at four nitrogen sources against *E. coli* FNCC-19.

2018). The highest bacteriocin production and activity were obtained after 30h of incubation at 30°C with the use of 2.2-g peptone as a nitrogen source (Fahim *et al.* 2017). In the MRSB with soybean meal, maximal bacteriocin production from *L. brevis* against *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *Serratia marcescens* was obtained (Namasivayam *et al.* 2014).

The effect of carbon source on the growth of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 and its bacteriocin antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* is presented in Figure 2. Strain 2397 grew with or without various carbon sources and had nearly identical absorbance values ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that MRSB has enough C sources to support LAB's growth, particularly strain 2397 (Figure 2A).

Although the absorbance value was roughly similar, the addition of diverse C sources significantly ($p < 0.05$)

enhanced strain 2397's antibacterial activity against *E. coli* FNCC-19 (Figure 2B). With the addition of a carbon source, more sugar becomes accessible for strain 2397 to utilize as an energy source and synthesize bacteriocins. This study showed the highest antimicrobial activity of bacteriocin from strain 2397 against *E. coli* FNCC-19 with the addition of lactose. This result contradicts the finding of Fahim *et al.* (2017), which showed the highest activity of bacteriocin from *Enterococcus avium* HF86 obtained using 2% mannitol. Maximum bacteriocin production from *Lactobacillus brevis* against *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *Serratia marcescens* was recorded in MRS media with maltose (Namasivayam *et al.* 2014). This fact is most likely due to differences in the type of LAB strain.

The effect of the Tween type on the growth of strain 2397 and the resulting bacteriocin against *E. coli* is presented in Figure 3. Tweens 20 and 80 significantly increased ($p <$

Figure 2. Growth and antimicrobial activity of bacteriocin of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 at five carbon sources against *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19.

Figure 3. Growth and antimicrobial activity of bacteriocin of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 at three Tween sources against *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19.

0.05) the bacteriocin activity of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 against *E. coli* compared to control (without the addition of Tween). This study contrasts the findings of Parlindungan *et al.* (2021), who reported increased production and activity of bacteriocin *Lactiplantacillus plantarum* B21 against spoilage pathogenic bacterial strains with the addition of Tween. The addition of Tween 80 to MRSB could increase the antimicrobial activity of bacteriocins from *Lactobacillus acidophilus* CH1 and *Lactobacillus fermentum* M1 against various pathogenic bacteria, including *E. coli* (Hoda *et al.* 2013). The present study showed that the source of Tween did not significantly ($p > 0.05$) affect the growth of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397; however, in the study of Parlindungan *et al.* (2021), Tween could increase the growth of *L. plantarum* B21.

This finding may be due to differences in the genus and species of LAB used in the studies (Juturu and Wu 2018; Balciunas *et al.* 2013).

The average protein, moisture, and ash contents of fish balls after DMRT at the 5% level are presented in Table 2. The ANOVA showed that the concentration of bacteriocins, storage times, and their interactions significantly affected protein content. The higher the concentration of bacteriocin used, the ammonium sulfate higher the protein content of fish balls. This fact is because bacteriocin is a simple protein produced by certain bacteria. Bacteriocin from strain 2397 is a low-molecular-weight peptide having a molecular mass of 14.4 kDa (Pato *et al.* 2021b). Because bacteriocin is a protein molecule, increasing the bacteriocin concentration

Table 2. The chemical composition of fish balls added various concentrations of bacteriocin during frozen storage.

Concentration of bacteriocin	Protein content (%) at				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	8.79 ^a	8.82 ^{h,i}	8.08 ^k	9.63 ^d	8.91^a
0.15%	9.87 ^c	9.55 ^{d,e}	8.39 ^j	9.64 ^d	9.36^b
0.30%	9.24 ^f	8.99 ^{g,h}	9.86 ^c	9.41 ^{e,f}	9.39^c
0.45%	10.16 ^a	10.20 ^b	9.74 ^{c,d}	10.19 ^b	10.14^d
0.60%	10.18 ^b	8.65 ⁱ	9.03 ^g	10.9 ^a	10.29^e
Average	9.65^c	9.26^b	9.02^a	9.95^d	
Concentration of bacteriocin	Moisture content (%) at				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	69.38 ^{b,c,d,e}	72.95 ^a	67.56 ^f	69.58 ^{b,c,d,e}	69.87^a
0.15%	68.14 ^{e,f}	70.09 ^{b,c,d}	69.19 ^{c,d,e,f}	70.03 ^{b,c,d}	69.37^a
0.30%	68.97 ^{d,e,f}	69.06 ^{d,e,f}	69.75 ^{b,c,d,e}	70.43 ^{b,c,d}	69.55^a
0.45%	69.79 ^{b,c,d,e}	70.49 ^{b,c,d}	70.31 ^{b,c,d}	69.71 ^{b,c,d,e}	70.07^a
0.60%	71.02 ^b	70.49 ^{b,c,d}	68.15 ^{e,f}	70.82 ^{b,c}	70.12^a
Average	69.46^{b,c}	70.62^a	68.99^c	70.11^{a,b}	
Concentration of bacteriocin	Ash contents (%) at				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	0.86 ^{g,h}	0.98 ^{d,e,f,g,h}	0.94 ^{e,f,g,h}	0.82 ^h	0.90^c
0.15%	0.92 ^{f,g,h}	1.11 ^{b,c,d,e}	1.07 ^{c,d,e,f}	1.07 ^{c,d,e,f}	1.04^b
0.30%	1.06 ^{c,d,e,f}	1.18 ^{a,b,c}	1.03 ^{c,d,e,f}	1.07 ^{c,d,e,f}	1.08^b
0.45%	1.04 ^{c,d,e,f}	1.18 ^{5a,b,c}	0.99 ^{d,e,f,g}	1.08 ^{c,d,e,f}	1.09^b
0.60%	1.25 ^{a,b}	1.12 ^{a,b,c,d}	1.28 ^a	1.19 ^{a,b,c}	1.20^a
Average	1.03^b	1.11^a	1.06^{a,b}	1.05^{a,b}	

Means followed by the lowercase letters indicate a significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

boosted the catfish meatballs' protein content. Table 2 clearly illustrated that storage time substantially impacted protein content. The protein content of fish balls decreased significantly during storage at 6 d. This finding is most likely due to the protein employed as a nitrogen source for microbial development during storage, which increased over time. On Day 9, however, protein levels began to rise again. This fact is most likely due to the growing quantity of bacteria and the prolonged storage time (Noordin *et al.* 2014; Pato *et al.* 2020b, 2022). Protein components and nitrogen-containing chemicals make up microbes. The total protein content in fish balls was calculated as the protein content of molecules containing N in microorganisms at the moment of protein analysis (Table 2). According to the Indonesian National Standard, fish balls must have at least 9% protein. Table 2 demonstrates that practically all treatments fulfilled the standard, except the treatment without bacteriocin on storage Days 0, 3, and 6; 0.15% bacteriocin treatment on Day 6; and treatment 0.30% 0.60% on Day 3, respectively. In this study, protein

levels in fish balls were nearly identical to those reported by Yarosita *et al.* (2004), notably in non-bacteriocin-treated fish balls, at 8.22–9.26%.

Moisture content is one of the most critical factors that affect the texture, flavor, stability, and shelf life of food (Winarno 2008). The ANOVA showed that the concentration of bacteriocins, storage time, and their interactions significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected the moisture content of fish balls (Table 2). The findings in this table reveal that bacteriocin concentration did not significantly ($p > 0.05$) impact the average moisture content of catfish meatballs. This phenomenon could be because bacteriocins did not contain water or could not bind water, which could cause levels to rise as bacteriocin concentrations rise. Storage time has a significant effect on the moisture content of fish balls. The lowest average decrease in moisture content was obtained after frozen storage on Day 6. This fact was probably due to microbes, including *E. coli* (Table 3), which used water for their growth. On the ninth day of frozen storage, the moisture content increased

again. This fact is probably due to microbial growth-producing water as one of the metabolic products. The moisture content of fish balls in this investigation ranged from 68.14–71.02%, lower than Farareza’s (2018) finding of 74.45–76.01%. The high moisture content in Farareza’s study was most likely owing to the inclusion of *sago* flour as extra raw material in the manufacturing of fish balls, whereas we used tapioca (Farareza 2018). The addition of bacteriocin until 0.30% to fish balls during storage at freezing temperature has met the Indonesian national standard (National Standardization Agency 2017), which says that the maximum water content is 70%. Other treatments slightly exceeded the existing standards, with a range of 70.07–70.72%.

Ash is an inorganic residue produced by the high-temperature burning of different minerals, with varying proportions according to the type and source of food (Andarwulan *et al.* 2011). The ANOVA showed that the concentration of bacteriocins, storage times, and their interactions significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected ash content. The higher the concentration of bacteriocin used, the

higher the average ash content of fish balls. This fact is due to crude bacteriocins, which most likely still contain sulfur residues in ammonium sulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$) (Pato *et al.* 2020a, 2021a). The more crude bacteriocin used, the higher the amount of S, which contributed to the increase in ash content in fish balls. The longer the frozen storage, the higher the ash content. This increase in ash content came from the mineral content of microbes that grew during frozen storage. In this investigation, the ash content ranged from 0.86–1.19. This study’s ash percentage was lower than that of Farareza (2018), who found that the ash concentration in fish balls ranged from 1.68–1.83%. Although both employ catfish to make fish balls, the difference could be the amount and type of extra ingredients used such as salt and seasonings.

The number of pathogenic and spoilage microbes is one of the quality parameters for fish balls, and the results of the study are presented in Table 3. The higher the bacteriocin concentration employed, the lower the TPC value in fish balls. This fact is because the fish balls matrix contains more bacteriocin, which inhibits microbial growth.

Table 3. Microbial counts of fish balls added various concentrations of bacteriocin and stored at frozen temperature.

Concentration of bacteriocin	Total plate count (x 10 ² CFU/g)				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	3.17	3.80	3.57	4.12	3.67
0.15%	1.43	1.92	1.67	1.52	1.64
0.30%	0.53	1.20	1.22	1.67	1.16
0.45%	0.37	1.22	1.02	1.38	0.99
0.60%	0.20	0.27	0.82	0.95	0.56
Average	1.14	1.68	1.66	1.93	

Concentration of bacteriocin	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (CFU/g)				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	0	0	0	0	0
0.15%	0	0	0	0	0
0.30%	0	0	0	0	0
0.45%	0	0	0	0	0
0.60%	0	0	0	0	0
Average	0	0	0	0	

Concentration of bacteriocin	<i>E. coli</i> (MPN/g)				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	14,7	0	8.3	0	5.8
0.15%	7,7	0	7.7	0	3,9
0.30%	13,0	0	0	0	3.2
0.45%	10.7	0	0	0	2.7
0.60%	0	0	0	0	0
Average	9.2	0	3.2	0	

Bacteriocins produced by *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* and *L. monocytogenes in vitro* (Pato *et al.* 2020a, 2021a). This bacteriocin is thought to suppress microbes that cause damage to fish balls because it can inhibit pathogenic bacteria. As a result, the more bacteriocins utilized, the lower the TPC in fish balls. The lowest TPC was obtained in the treatment using 0.60% bacteriocin with an average of 0.56×10^2 CFU/g. Table 3 also shows that the longer the storage time at frozen temperatures, the higher the TPC of fish balls with an average value of 1.93×10^2 CFU/g – with the highest TPC value obtained in the treatment without the use of bacteriocins of 4.12×10^2 CFU/g and the lowest on the use of 0.60% bacteriocin at 0.95×10^2 CFU/g. This finding indicates that the length of storage and the higher the concentration of bacteriocin used, the lower the TPC.

Bacteriocin from *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 reduced the growth of *S. aureus* in an *in vitro* test (Pato *et al.* 2020b). However, no *S. aureus* growth was seen in fish balls treated with or without bacteriocin, as shown in Table 3. The lack of development of *S. aureus* in all fishball samples treatments was most likely due to appropriate sanitation and hygiene standards during the manufacturing process. Contaminated surfaces contribute to the transmission of harmful microorganisms in the food industry (WHO 2007). Pathogenic bacteria such as *S. aureus* were mainly found to spread through the hands of food workers in the food industry and restaurants (Kadariya *et al.* 2014). Hand hygiene, washing, and disinfection are prerequisites for hygiene management in the food industry to lower the risk of food-borne infections (WHO 2021). In all treatments, *S. aureus* has met the quality standard of 10^2 CFU/g for fish balls.

E. coli is one of the indicators of sanitation and hygiene in food processing. The results showed that the higher the concentration of bacteriocin used, the lower the number of *E. coli* in fish balls (Table 3). On the ninth day of frozen storage, the highest average number of *E. coli* was 5.8 MPN/g found in the treatment without bacteriocin, and the lowest number in the 0.60% bacteriocin treatment was 0 MPN/g. The result shows that using 0.60% bacteriocin could inhibit growth during the storage of fish balls at freezing temperatures from Day 0–9. This finding is consistent with the results of an *in vitro* study, which found that bacteriocin from *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397 could inhibit growth by adding various sources of nitrogen, carbon, and Tween (Figures 1–3). The use of bacteriocin concentrations of 0.45–0.60% resulted in the number of *E. coli* that had met the quality standard of fish balls, *i.e.* a maximum of 3 MPN/g.

The appearance, smell, taste, and texture have an essential role in products as markers of damage, quality level instructions, and processing process guidelines – and

can influence people’s perceptions of the quality of a food product (Setyaningsih *et al.* 2010; Andarwulan *et al.* 2011). The results of a sensory test of fish balls added various concentrations of bacteriocin stored at frozen temperature are shown in Table 4.

The ANOVA showed that the bacteriocin concentration and the interaction between bacteriocin concentration and frozen storage significantly affected appearance, but storage time did not significantly influence the appearance of fish balls (Table 4). However, we can look at the range of appearance values ranging from 6.8–7.6 – indicating that the appearance of fish balls was a slightly smooth surface, slightly hollow, and slightly bright. This finding means that the appearance of fish balls is almost the same for all treatments of bacteriocin concentrations and freezing storage times. The variance results showed variations in bacteriocin concentrations, storage times, and interaction significantly affected fish balls’ odor, taste, and texture (Table 4). The odor value ranged from 7.2–7.8 in all treatments, descriptively indicating that the fish balls had a “slightly product-specific” odor. The specific odor comes from the catfish used in making fish balls. The distinctive odor of fish meat in the form of mud comes from the abundance of blue-green algae phytoplankton from the genera *Mycrocystis*, *Anabaena*, and *Oscillatoria* produce geosmin compounds (Jiang *et al.* 2006). This geosmin compound produces an earthy odorant in processed fish meat products such as fish balls.

Likewise, the taste test with a value range of 6.8–7.4 showed that the fish balls showed a “somewhat product-specific” taste. The specific taste of these fish balls mainly originated from catfish taste. The use of several spices such as pepper and garlic contributed to the smell and taste of fish balls. Raw garlic is full of sulfur compounds, including allicin that gives raw garlic its bitter taste (Cho and Lee 2009). Piperine, piperidine, and chavicin – which are piperine constituents – are responsible for pepper’s spicy taste (Wahyuni and Yury 2013). Texture with a value range from 6.8–7.8 indicates that the meatball has a “solid, compact, slightly chewy” texture. The protein content of 16.08% in catfish contributes to texture formation in meatballs. Catfish protein consists of essential and non-essential amino acids that function in the formation of texture in fish balls and also plays a role in the fulfillment of complete amino acids when consumed (Lukman 2017). The formation of a solid, compact, slightly chewy texture in fish balls was also due to the contribution of tapioca added in the meatball processing. Tapioca has properties such as being sticky and able to form a gel so that tapioca is often added in making meatballs (Kusnandar 2006).

Table 4. Sensory evaluation of fish balls added various concentrations of bacteriocin and stored at frozen temperature.

Concentration of bacteriocin	Appearance				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	6.6 ^{b,c}	7.6 ^{a,b}	7.6 ^{a,b}	7.4 ^{a,b,c}	7.3^a
0.15%	7.2 ^{a,b,c}	6.6 ^{b,c}	7.0 ^{a,b,c}	6.4 ^c	6.8^b
0.30%	6.8 ^{a,b,c}	7.0 ^{a,b,c}	7.0 ^{a,b,c}	6.8 ^{a,b,c}	6.9^{a,b}
0.45%	7.6 ^{a,b}	6.6 ^{b,c}	7.0 ^{a,b,c}	6.8 ^{a,b,c}	7.0^{a,b}
0.60%	7.0 ^{a,b,c}	7.8 ^a	7.0 ^{a,b,c}	7.0 ^{a,b,c}	7.2^{a,b}
Average	7.0^a	7.1^a	7.1^a	6.7^a	
Concentration of bacteriocin	Odor				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	7.4	7.6	7.4	7.4	7.5
0.15%	7.4	7.2	7.2	7.4	7.3
0.30%	7.6	7.2	7.4	7.8	7.5
0.45%	7.6	7.0	7.4	7.4	7.4
0.60%	7.4	7.2	7.2	7.8	7.4
Average	7.5	7.2	7.3	7.6	
Concentration of bacteriocin	Taste				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	6.8	6.8	6.8	6.6	6.8
0.15%	7.6	7.6	7.6	6.8	7.2
0.30%	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0
0.45%	7.0	7.0	7.2	6.8	7.0
0.60%	7.4	7.0	7.4	7.0	7.2
Average	7.2^a	6.9	7.2	6.8	
Concentration of bacteriocin	Texture				
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Average
0.0%	7.4	7.0	7.4	7.6	7.4
0.15%	7.4	7.4	7.4	7.0	7.3
0.30%	7.0	7.0	7.0	6.6	6.9
0.45%	7.8	6.8	7.4	7.2	7.3
0.60%	7.2	7.8	7.4	7.2	7.4
Average	7.4	7.2	7.3	7.1	

Means followed by the lowercase letters indicate a significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION

The addition of four nitrogen, five carbon, or three tween sources did not affect the growth of *P. pentosaceus* strain 2397. However, they could increase the antimicrobial activity of bacteriocin. The addition of peptone, beef extract or ammonium sulfate, lactose, or Tween 80 into MRSB optimally increased the bacteriocin antimicrobial activity of strain 2397 against *E. coli*. The concentration of bacteriocins, storage time, and interactions significantly affected fish balls' protein, moisture, and ash contents; however, they did not influence the odor, taste, and texture.

The use of bacteriocins, particularly at a concentration of 0.60%, produced better fish balls during initial storage at freezing temperature than no bacteriocin.

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REFERENCES

- ANDARWULAN N, KUSNANDAR F, HERAWATI D. 2011. Food Analysis. PT. Dian Rakyat. Jakarta.
- AOAC. 1999. Official methods of analysis, 16th ed. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington.
- AOAC. 2005. Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International. 18th ed. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Arlington.
- BALCIUNAS EM, CASTILLO MARTINEZ FA, TODOROV SD, FRANCO A, CONVERTI BDGDM, OLIVEIRA RPDS. 2013. Novel biotechnological applications of bacteriocins: a review. Food Control 32(1): 134–142.
- BHARTI V, MEHTA A, SINGH S, JAIN N, AHIRWA L, MEHTA S. 2015. Bacteriocin: a novel approach for preservation of food. International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 7(9): 20–29.
- [CDC] Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2012. Escherichia coli. National Center for Emerging and Zoonotic Infectious Diseases. Atlanta, GA.
- CHO J, LEE SK. 2009. Separation of Blue Pigments in Crushed Garlic Cloves: the Color-forming Potential of Individual Amino Acids. Proceeding 2nd IS on Human Health Effects of FAV. Pati B ed. Acta Horticulturae 841: 491–493.
- FAHIM HA, WALEED M, ROUBY AE, EL-GENDY AO, KHAIRALLAH AS, NAGUIB IA, FARGHALI AA. 2017. Enhancement of the productivity of the potent bacteriocin avicin A and improvement of its stability using nanotechnology approaches. Scientific Reports 7(1): 1–13. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-017-10157-9
- FARAREZA JR. 2018. Physical, chemical and organoleptic characteristics of fish balls (*Pangasius pangasius*) with sago flour substitution [thesis]. Brawijaya University, Malang, Indonesia.
- FAUZIYAH A. 2019. The effect of the amount of sago flour (*Metroxylon sago* Rottb) and the amount of spinach (*Amaranthus spp.*) on the organoleptic properties of spinach cork fish meatballs. E-Journal Boga 5(3): 1–10.
- FENG P, WEAGANT S, GRANT M. 2002. Enumeration of *Escherichia coli* and the coliform bacteria. Bacteriological Analytical Manual, 8th ed. FDA/Center for Food Safety & Applied Nutrition. Archived from the original on 19 May 2009.
- G'ALVEZ A, ABRIQUEL H, LOPEZ RL, OMAR NB. 2007. Bacteriocin-based strategies for food biopreservation. International Journal of Food Microbiology 120(1–2): 51–70.
- HODAAM, EL-MONGY MA, HAMZA HA. 2013. Study bacteriocin production and optimization using new isolates of *Lactobacillus* spp. isolated from some dairy products under different culture conditions. Scientific Research 4(3): 342–356.
- HOSONO A, WARDOYO R, OTANI H. 1989. Microbial flora in “*dadih*”, a traditional fermented milk in Indonesia. Lebensmittel Wiss. u-Technology 23: 149–153.
- HUDA N, ABDULLAH A, BABJI AS. 2001. Physico-chemical properties of Malaysian fish balls. Fishery Technology 38(1): 14–17.
- HUDA N, SHEN YH, HUEY YL, DEWI RS. 2010. Ingredients, proximate composition, colour and textural properties of commercial Malaysian fish balls. Pakistan Journal of Nutrition 9(12): 1182–1186.
- INDONESIAN CENTRAL STATISTICS AGENCY. 2021. Production of catfish in Indonesia and Riau. Retrieved from <https://www.bps.go.id>
- ISO 7251. 2005. Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of presumptive *Escherichia coli* — most probable number technique.
- JIANG J, HE X, CANE DE. 2006. Geosmin biosynthesis. *Streptomyces coelicolor* germacradienol/germacrene D synthase converts farnesyl diphosphate to geosmin. Journal of the American Chemical Society 128(25): 8128–8129.
- JUTURU V, WU JC. 2018. Microbial Production of Bacteriocins: Latest Research Development and Applications. Biotechnology Advances 36(8): 2187–2200. DOI: 10.1016/j.biotechadv.2018.10.007
- KADARIYA J, SMITH TC, THAPALIYA D. 2014. *Staphylococcus aureus* and Staphylococcal food-borne disease: an ongoing challenge in public health. BioMed Research International, 827965. DOI: 10.1155/2014/827965
- KUSNANDAR F. 2006. Modification of Starch and Its Application in the Food Industry. Food Review Indonesia.
- LUKMAN S. 2017. Utilization of fish protein concentrate from patin fish (*Pangasius hypophthalmus*) on street foods for under five years children at Kampar District, Riau Province. International Journal of Oceans and Oceanography 11(1): 75–88.
- MORSY MK, MEKAWIE, ELSABAGH R. 2017. Impact of pomegranate peel nanoparticles on quality attributes of meatballs during refrigerated storage. LWT – Food Science and Technology 89: 489–495. DOI: 10.1016/j.lwt.2017.11.022

- NAMASIVAYAM SKR, ANGEL JCR, BHARANI RSA, KARTHIK MY. 2014. Effect of media on bacteriocin production by *Lactobacillus brevis* and evaluation of antibacterial activity. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences* 5(5): 1129–1136.
- NATIONAL STANDARDIZATION AGENCY. 2017. Quality Standard of Fish Meatball. Fish meatball SNI 7266:2017.
- NOORDIN WNM, SHUNMUGAM N, HUDA N. 2014. Application of salt solution and vacuum packaging in extending the shelf-life of cooked fish balls for home and retail uses. *Journal of Food Quality* 37(6): 444–452.
- PARLINDUNGAN E, DEKIWADIA C, JONER OAH. 2021. Some factors that influence growth and bacteriocin production in *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* B21. *Process Biochemistry* 107: 18–26.
- PATO U, JOHAN VS, KHAIRUNNISA F, HASIBUAN RDH. 2017. Antibiotic resistance and antibacterial activity of *dadih* originated *Lactobacillus casei* subsp. *casei* R-68 against food-borne pathogens. *Asian Journal of Microbiology Biotechnology and Environmental Science* 19(3): 577–587.
- PATO U, YUSMARINI Y, FITRIANI S, JONNADI NN, WAHYUNI MS, FERUNI JA, JASWIR I. 2020a. Inhibitory activity of crude bacteriocin produced by lactic acid bacteria isolated from *dadih* against *Listeria monocytogenes*. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity* 21(4): 1295–1302. DOI: 10.13057/bio div/d210404
- PATO U, YUSMARINI Y, FITRIANI S, FAUZI DA, ISMADIAH G, HIDAYAH M, SABILIANI W. 2022. Evaluation of bacteriocin produced by *Pediococcus pentosaceus* strain 2397 as natural preservative for fish meatballs stored at room temperature. *Advances in Biological Sciences Research* 16: 342–347.
- PATO U, YUSMARINI Y, FITRIANI S, TARTILA, YENI R, FADILLAH F, HUSNANINI L. 2020b. Enhancement of the growth and antimicrobial activity of *P. pentosaceus* Strain 2397 against *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Biotechnology (Faisalabad)* 20(1): 8–14. DOI: 10.3923/biotech.2021.8.14
- PATO U, YUSMARINI Y, FITRIANI S, JONNADI NN, WAHYUNI MS, FERUNI JA, JASWIR I. 2021a. Antimicrobial activity of lactic acid bacteria strains isolated from *dadih* against *Escherichia coli*. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 709: 012019. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/709/1/012019
- PATO U, RIFTYAN E, AYU DF, JONNADI NN, WAHYUNI MS, FERUNI JA, ABDEL-WAHHAB MA. 2021b. Antibacterial efficacy of lactic acid bacteria and bacteriocin isolated from *dadih*'s against *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Food Science and Technology*, 2061: 10–15. DOI: 10.1590/fst.27121
- PEREZ RH, ZENDO T, SONOMOTO K. 2014. Novel bacteriocins from lactic acid bacteria (LAB): various structures and applications. *Microbial Cell Factories* 13(Suppl 1): S1–S3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1475-2859-13-S1-S3>. PMID:25186038
- RAHARDIANTO A, ABDULGANI, NURLITA, TRI-SYANI N. 2012. Effect of the honey solution concentration in physiological NaCl on viability and mobility of catfish (*Pangasius pangasius*) spermatozoa during storage. *Jurnal Sains dan Seni ITS* 1(1): 2301-928X.
- RIOS AC, MOUTINHO CG, PINTO FC, DEL FIOLE FS *et al.* 2016. Alternatives to overcoming bacterial resistances: state-of-the-art. *Microbiological Research* 191: 51–80. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2016.04.008>. PMID:27524653
- SAEED M, KHAN WA, SHABBIR MA, KHAN MI, RANDHAWA MA, YASMIN I. 2014. Bacteriocins as a natural antimicrobial agent in food preservation: a review. *Pakistan Journal of Food Sciences* 24(4): 244–255.
- SANKAR NR, PRIYANKA VD, REDDY PS, RAJANIKANTH P, KUMAR VK, INDIRA M. 2012. Purification and characterization of bacteriocin produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum* isolated from cow milk. *International Journal of Microbiological Research* 3(2): 133–137.
- SETYANINGSIH D, APRIANTONO A, SUPRAPTO MP. 2010. *Sensory Analysis for the Food and Agro Industry*. Institut Pertanian Bogor-Press. Bogor.
- SINAGA DD, HERPANDI, NOPIANTI R. 2017. Characteristics of fish balls (*Pangasius pangasius*) with the addition of carrageenan, soy protein isolate, and sodium tripolyphosphate. *Jurnal Teknologi Hasil Perikanan* 6(1): 1–13.
- SINGLETON P. 1999. *Bacteria in Biology, Biotechnology and Medicine*, 5th ed. Wiley. p. 444–454.
- STILES ME. 1996. Biopreservation by lactic acid bacteria. In: Antonie van Leeuwenhoek. *International Journal of General and Molecular Microbiology* 70(2–4): 331–345.
- TENAILLON O, SKURNIK D, PICARD B, DENAMUR E. 2010. The population genetics of commensal *Escherichia coli*. *Nature Reviews. Microbiology* 8(3): 207–217.

- THOMPSON A. 2007. *E. coli* thrives in beach sands. Live Science. Retrieved on 03 Dec 2007.
- VOGTL, DIPPOLD L. 2005. *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 outbreak associated with consumption of ground beef, June–July 2002. Public Health Reports 120(2): 174–178.
- WAHYUNI Y, YURY ARB. 2013. Metabolomics and molecular marker analysis to explore pepper (*Capsicum* sp.). Biodiversity 9(1): 130–144. DOI: 10.1007/s11306-012-0432-6
- WINARNO FG. 2008. Food Chemistry and Nutrition. Bogor, Indonesia: M-Brio Press.
- [WHO] World Health Organization. 2011. Nitrate and Nitrite in Drinking-water. Geneva: WHO Press.
- [WHO] World Health Organization. 2007. Improved hand hygiene to prevent healthcare-associated infections. Patient Safety Solutions 1(9). Retrieved on 02 Aug 2021 from <http://www.who.int/patientsafety/solutions/patientsafety/PS-Solution9.pdf>
- YAROSITA FS, RINDY PT, BUSTAMI, WINARTI Z. 2004. Quality of patin fish meats irradiated with gamma lights (^{60}Co). Proceedings of the Scientific Seminar on Research and Development of Isotope and Radiation Applications; Jakarta, Indonesia.